

METHODS OF PREPARATION OF FUTURE PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGISTS FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH

Turakhonova B.

Teacher at Andijan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14561298>

Abstract. *In this article, the technology of preparing future pedagogues-psychologists for the organization of educational activities, clarifying the purpose of activity, designing the content of spiritual culture, clarifying the means of pedagogical influence, developing methods and ways of organizing student activities, activity results monitoring is discussed.*

Keywords: *environment, spiritual-cultural activity, variety, emotions, world, pedagogy, technology, behavior, consciousness, self-management.*

The preparation of future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities is directly related to objective, external factors (environment, joint action with people in different types of spiritual and cultural activities), as well as subjective, internal factors (the individual's feelings, awareness of the need to move in harmony with the universe, personal strength and opportunities for description and assessment). That is why pedagogy as a leading factor in the development of spiritual culture in students of higher educational institutions reflects, on the one hand, the conscious management of their behavior and the practical activity of the individual, on the other hand.

It was concluded that the implementation of the technology for preparing future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities should be based on the following pedagogical conditions: clarifying the purpose of the activity; designing the content of spiritual culture; clarifying the means of pedagogical influence; developing methods and ways of organizing student activities; monitoring the results of activities.

As priority areas of technology, the following were identified:

- 1) harmonizing with reasonable exactingness and active interaction;
- 2) collaborative development activities of professors and students;
- 3) self-management; organization and results of activities;
- 4) giving up direct coercion as a method.

These peculiarities of preparing future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities are reflected in axiological, personality and activity-oriented approaches. The axiological approach combines a number of universal values, such as justice, goodness, beauty, life, freedom, happiness, and is manifested in the transmission of spiritual and universal values from generation to generation. This approach is realized through the understanding of the individual as a self-value and the principles of enriching the educational and cognitive activities of students with spiritual content. The personality-oriented approach helps to develop and self-develop personality, taking into account individual identities, independently determine the goals of their activities and implement them. It is this approach that allows the individual to access freedom of choice as well as responsibility and active interaction. The activity-oriented approach

assumes the acquisition of the social experience gained by the student's process of personal activity and as a result. Because all personal qualities in a student are manifested not only in his activities, but also take shape in this process.

In order to achieve the expected results based on this technology, it is advisable to consider the pedagogical conditions for the development of spiritual culture. Based on the results of the analysis, the following are identified as necessary and important conditions:

1) creation of a facilitation in educational environment for the preparation of future educators-psychologists for the organization of educational activities;

2) freedom to choose a form of work related to the preparation of future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities;

3) attracting students to types of work beyond the audience in order to prepare future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities;

4) the spiritual mutual support and cooperation of educators-psychologists and cadets.

The implementation of these conditions ensures the content of the emotive, behavioral motor and mental components of the preparation of future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities.

The emotive component reflects the emotional-value-oriented attitude of the individual to the activity, the assessment of the importance of external and internal influences for life, as well as achievements in spiritual culture as an important mechanism for preparing future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities. The behavioral component covers the skills of spiritual activity planning, self-control, reflection, personal awareness. The mental component serves to understand the importance of spiritual and moral values that allow the formation of a new experience, its relationship with objective and subjective laws.

The components of the preparation of future educators-psychologists for the organization of educational activities are formed on the basis of certain types of activities. The emotive component is formed by the perception of realities associated with educational activities, the study of patterns of art, literature, creative activity. Compliance with ethics and executive discipline ensures the formation of a behavioral component and serves to unlock individual abilities. The analysis of sources on spiritual culture, the creation of samples of spiritual culture, participation in various charitable events and promotions stimulate the formation of a mental component. Each type of activity related to spiritual culture serves to content the creative, social and personal experience of knowledge in students.

The design and forecasting of results as a theoretical and methodological basis of the technology for preparing future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities reflects the integrity of the pedagogical process in itself, the integrated goal, approaches, principles, pedagogical conditions, periodicity of activity, stages of the formation of experiences of spiritual and practical activity.

The stages of preparing future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities in themselves represent the following sequence of algorithms: motivational-need, motive and goal; analysis of guiding-conditions (methods of action), development of an action program (methods and tools); practical – collective, individual, group and independent activities; control – correctional stage-analysis of results, assessment and reflexive behavior.

The purpose of the motivational stage is to instill motivation for the organization of educational activities in future pedagogical psychologists. The main tasks of this stage can include

the formation of a positive attitude in students towards activities related to spiritual culture, preparation for the perception of values, resources related to spiritual culture, understanding the practical importance of this activity.

The purpose of the guiding stage is to ensure the integrity of the process of involving future pedagogical psychologists in the organization of educational activities. At this stage, students find the content of orientation towards value. At this stage, in connection with the goal, plan and content, students are formed skills for independent acquisition of knowledge, systematization and their creative use, selection of methods of action.

Practical-activity stage in pedagogical activity, the development and improvement of general competence in the organization of educational activities in future pedagogical psychologists, the creation of author's developments (event scenarios, projects, creative works) on spiritual culture, satisfaction with activities, awareness of responsibility and positive emotions on the professional sphere are formed.

The control-correction stage of technology is associated with the analysis and assessment of the results of practical activities mastered by students and filling gaps, eliminating shortcomings.

In modern pedagogical science, the forms and methods of organizing educational activities have a rich variety. The classification proposed by N.M.Boritko [10] in the process of test-experimental work was supplemented by the feature of basic educational activities, forms and methods corresponding to the needs and capabilities of students. The forms were presented in three groups: public (flashmobs, holidays, events); collective (club days, trainings, etc.); individual (participation with exercises, speeches, presentations, etc). They allow students to form a positive attitude towards their future professional activities, realize themselves in the socio-professional space and take their rightful place, form general professional competencies.

The above listed forms of educational activity were widely used in the educational system of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Samarkand State University, Samarkand State Institute of foreign languages.

Flashmob is a relatively new form of educational activity (translated from English precisely as "instant publicity"). Students are attracted by the fact that this form gives them the opportunity to show themselves in an unusual, creative way. In this way, for example, students of Andijan State University actively participated in flashmobs organized by the youth work department (dedicated to "Donor Day", "The Day of the defender of the Fatherland" and other flashmobs). Participation in flashmobs has developed communicative competencies, abilities, skills for quick decision-making in non-standard situations.

It is especially important to make the most effective use of effective methods in the organization of educational activities. We have presented the methods used in the educational process in four groups:

- reflexive: explanation, dramatization, essay, case-study, dispute, debate;
- project: training, social tests, training projects, "mental attack", business game;
- valuable: encouragement, dialogue, rewarding;
- complex: consultation, analysis of pedagogical situations, educational situations.

One of the main features of the mentioned methods is that they are based on an activity-oriented approach.

Based on a competency-based approach, we will consider the experience of applying various methods in the process of preparing future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities.

In universities, where experimental objects are calculated, a lot of attention is paid to the work of a tutor. At today's stage in the development of education, the group tutor is an important subset of the institution of higher education system, it influences the life activities of the group, is responsible for the strengthening of educational functions in the development of self-management. At the pedagogical faculties of Andijan, Fergana, Namangan state universities, a program of tutor hours for 1-3 year students is compiled, which ensures the effective application of various methods in educational work.

When working with first-year students, the elements of case-study, business game, educational projects, "mental attack", training were actively used. The mentioned methods made it possible to act together in a social group without conflicts, to create a favorable positive climate in the team.

In this way, when holding a roundtable on the topic of some, for example, "Strategy for behavior in conflict situations", the coaches used the case-study method. The case-study method helps students to work with information, engage in discussion and debate, as well as make decisions in non-standard situations, think creatively.

Games were actively used by coaches as a method of educational activities. "Game play is a form of creation of the subject and social content of professional activity in the educational process, the modeling of the system of relations inherent in this type of labor" (A.A.Verbitsky[10]). Practical experience has shown that the imitation model in the form of a game reflects the social relationships that arise in the pedagogical process, and also reveals the social role and professional interests of the participants. This method of educational work is recommended to be widely used in tutoring hours dedicated to the problems of socio-psychological and professional training in higher educational institutions.

It was recommended to include the game "Student" in the program of training tutors with the first-year students at the experimental test facilities. It helps students realize the motivation to choose their own direction, to enter student life by going through stages from adapting to a new social environment to designing their graduation qualification work. This game also helped freshmen get acquainted with the activities of all the training and auxiliary departments of the higher education institution.

Special attention was paid to the implementation of the following in the process of joint educational activities of tutor and student in business games:

- mastering the experience of carrying out future professional activities by students;
- integration of existing and newly acquired theoretical knowledge, skills and qualities in students into a holistic system of universal competencies;
- improving the skill of acting together in a team without conflict;
- mastering the experience of social relations;
- formation of the ability to make quick and effective decisions together.

Tutors were also advised to use more of the dialogue method during coaching and morale hours.

Within the framework of the hours of tutoring and spirituality, more interactive lectures are used (lecture-conference, lecture-meditation, lecture-dialogue, lecture-essay). Lecture-

dialogue should not only form a holistic view of the reality under study, but also encourage feedback and search, arouse research interest in educational activities in the future educator (N.M.Boritko [10]). Lecture-dialogue serves as one of the most important means of motivating students to get an independent education. The advantage of lecture-dialogue is that the educator-tutor has the opportunity to direct communication with students. "The lecture-press conference method was used in the organization of the training on the topic mechanisms of personality adaptation". The tutor carried out the training based on questions submitted to the students in written form. At the beginning of the lecture, students were divided that the following questions were more interesting: "What are the emotions?" , "What appearances do emotions manifest?" , "What's the mood?", "What are the stages of stress?", etc.

In the course of this lecture, the teacher worked with each student individually, the information was heard by the student personally from the teacher, so the students took an active part in the training process. The lecture stimulated the thinking process of students, improved the correct distribution of attention, which is necessary for the formation of the competencies that are considered important for the future educator today.

A modern graduate of higher education institution should be the owner of such an important competence as the ability to make quick decisions in a constantly changing social environment. This ability was effectively formed in the process of application of the following set of methods: counseling, analysis of pedagogical situations, educational situations.

Particular importance was attached to the method of educational project in the preparation of future pedagogical psychologists for the organization of educational activities. First-year students of pedagogical faculties were taught at the initial stage to work in a team, to make quick decisions in non-standard situations. Second- and third-year students studied Social Design Technologies. The result of the application of social design was the creation of a social project, which gained significant practical importance for the participants. For example, 2-year students created the following projects in the master-student system: children's creative studio "Active house", children's club "Give children a smile!", advertising of a scientific and Technical Library in recreational areas of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute and others. In the 3rd year, students were able to participate in the activities of the upbringing laboratory, where they were given the opportunity to engage in social creativity, to realize the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired during their work with the tutor. Students considered the participants of the "upbringing" laboratory became organizers of such projects as the "student puppet theater", "football tournament", which are important for the entire higher education institution.

REFERENCES

1. Boritko N.M. Sistema professionalnogo vospitania V vuze. – M.: APKiPPRO, 2005. – 120 P.
2. Azizhodzhaeva N.N. Technology of preparation for the teacher's specialty. - T.: Tdpu named after Nizami, 2000. – 52 b.
3. Abdukodirov A. A., Pardayev A. X. Explanatory Dictionary of terms related to pedagogical technologies. - T.: Science and technology, 2012. – 44 b.
4. Verbitsky A.A. Lichnostny i kompetentnostny podkhodi v obrazovanii: problem integratsii / A.A. Verbitsky, O.G. Larionova M.: Logos, 2009. – 336 P.

5. Vitkovskaya N.G. Formirovaniye informatonnoy kompetentnosti studentov vuzov (na primere spesialnosti "journalism"): Autoref. dis. ... kand.ped.nauk. - Nizhny Novgorod: 2004. – 25 p.
6. Pedagogicheskie_tekhnologii//tekhnologijaindividualizacii_obuchenija_inge_unt_a_s_granickaja_v_d_shadrikov/12-1-0-58#.
7. <https://www.sovremennye-obrazovatelnye-tehnologi.ru/publ/metodicheskie-materialy/> <http://moi-color.ru/>
8. <http://www.eidos.ru/journal/2005/0910-12.htm>. - V nadzag: Centre distansionnogo obrazovaniya "Eydos", e-mail: list@eidos.ru
9. www.uza.uz.
10. www.nasas.com.
11. [tp://azps.ru/articles/pers/indexsz.html](http://azps.ru/articles/pers/indexsz.html).